

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE AMONG MEDICAL
STUDENTS ABOUT HEPATITIS B INFECTION AND
VACCINATION**¹Dr Saba Tahir, ²Dr Irha Saeed, ³Dr Bushra Iqbal¹Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan, ²Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan., ³Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Hepatitis B infection among healthcare professionals can be prevented through strategies such as vaccination, awareness-raising, and universal precautions. This study was conducted with newly admitted medical students to assess knowledge about HBV and to understand vaccination status. This opportunity was also used to motivate students to take the HBV vaccine, if not already taken, and to educate them about universal precautions.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted on newly admitted first-year MBBS students of Nishtar Medical University, Multan for six-months duration from March 2020 to August 2020. All students present on the date of data collection were included in the study and interviewed using a pre-tested questionnaire. Data were analyzed using percentages.

Results: Most of the students had a good understanding of diseases, transmission and prevention. Surprisingly, half of them were unaware of the high risk of passing the disease on to the doctor. Almost 40% of the students were unvaccinated, mainly due to a lack of awareness and motivation.

Conclusions: Vaccination against hepatitis B is recommended for all unvaccinated students starting their medical profession. An orientation and sensitization program should be carried out to increase awareness of HBV infection.

Keywords: attitude, hepatitis B, knowledge, medical students, vaccine

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Please cite this article in press Saba Tahir et al, *Knowledge And Attitude Among Medical Students About Hepatitis B Infection And Vaccination.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis B is an acute systemic infection with severe liver pathologies, caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV) and usually transmitted by the parenteral route [1-2]. Even after the discovery of an effective vaccine, it continues to pose a serious public health problem worldwide. Worldwide, more than 2 billion are infected and 350 million suffer from chronic diseases. About 6% of the world's population are carriers of HBV, which is approximately 80 million carriers [3]. Annually, approximately 500,000 to 1.2 million people die from chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma associated with chronic HBV infection. In Pakistan, the point prevalence is 2.1% and the carriage rate is 1.7%. Some studies have shown a higher carrier status, ranging from 11% in healthcare workers to 5% in the general population. HBV is highly contagious and transmitted by transdermal and transmucosal exposure to infected blood and other body fluids (ie semen and vaginal discharge) [4-5]. The most common routes of transmission are from mother to infant, unsafe injection practices, blood transfusions, and multiple sexual partners. 7-10 Healthcare workers are at high risk of contracting HBV. About 66,000 hepatitis B virus infections are reported annually due to needle stick injuries. A study of medical students found that 30% of reported needle-stick injuries occurred in an operating room [6-7]. The World Health Organization recommended that HBV vaccine be included in mass vaccination programs as a preventive tool for care workers, such as medical

students, can be prevented through strategies such as vaccination, awareness-raising and universal precautions. This study was conducted with newly admitted medical students to assess knowledge of HBV and to understand vaccination status. This opportunity was also used to motivate students to take the HBV vaccine, if not already taken, and to educate them about universal precautions.

METHODS:

It was a cross-sectional study conducted on students of Nishtar Medical University Multan for six-months duration from March 2020 to August 2020. In order to select newly admitted first-year students of MBBS (2019), the deliberate sampling method was used. The research covered all students willing to participate. Those who did not want to participate were excluded from the study. After giving informed consent, the study included 72 students present on the day of data collection. All of these students were interviewed using a pre-tested questionnaire and the data were analyzed using percentages.

RESULTS:

Most of the students were aware of the disease (100%), its causes (87.5%) and diagnostic tests (91.6%). The knowledge of the ideal age for vaccination against hepatitis B was correctly answered by 68.1% of students, while only 50% of students admitted that there is a high risk for doctors and medical staff (Table 1).

Table 1: Awareness about Hepatitis B.

Awareness	No	%
Heard about Hepatitis B	72	100
Caused by HBV	63	87.5
Diagnostic Tests available	66	91.6
Ideal age for vaccination	49	68.1
Doctors are at risk of infection	36	50

The media of 84.7% (television, internet, radio and newspapers) were the most common source of information indicating their importance in reaching the public opinion. Other sources were health workers (38.8%), friends and family (22.2%) (Table 2).

Table 2: Source of information about Hepatitis B.

Source of information	No	%
Media	61	84.7
Doctors / Health workers	28	38.8
Friends & Family	16	22.2
Others	14	19.4

94.4% of students agreed that HBV had spread through unsafe blood transfusions and sharing needles. Most of the students realized that HBV is also transmitted through unsafe sex (87.5%) and from a pregnant mother to a child (83.3%) (Table 3).

Table 3: Knowledge about modes of transmission.

Modes of transmission	No	%
Transfusion of Blood/ its products	68	94.4
Sharing of Needles / Intravenous drug users	68	94.4
Multiple Sex Partners	63	87.5
Mother to Child Transmission	60	83.3

Most of the students (98.6%) considered the jaundice vaccine to be a preventive measure. They also agreed that safe blood (95.8%), disposable needles (94.4%), safe sex (87.5%), and condoms (86.1%) were important preventive measures (Table 4).

Table 4: Awareness about preventive measures.

Awareness about Preventive measures	No	%
Use of Hepatitis B Vaccine	71	98.6
Safe Blood/ its products	69	95.8
Avoid Sharing of Needles intravenous drug users	68	94.4
Avoid Multiple Sex Partners	63	87.5
Use condoms	62	86.1

Almost 40.2% of the students were not vaccinated because of hepatitis B. The main reason given was lack of awareness (20.8%). Some students believed that vaccination was not necessary (12.5%) and few students (0.7%) neglected to vaccinate (Table 5).

Table 5: Reason for not taking Hepatitis B vaccination.

Reason	No	%
Not aware about vaccine	15	20.8
Considered Not necessary	9	12.5
Neglected	5	0.7
Total	29	40.2%

DISCUSSION:

In our study, general awareness of hepatitis B was good, but only half of the students were aware of the risks to healthcare professionals. In a study conducted in Syria, it was observed that among medical students in the first year, knowledge about HBV was 89.06%, and 67.1% correctly answered the causative factor⁸⁻¹⁰. These results show that students should be more aware of the risks to health professionals. Many studies, including ours, have shown the role of the media in spreading awareness. A study of married women in Jammu also found that friends, radio, television, newspapers, doctors and magazines were the sources of information for 20%, 10%, 35%, 5%, 25% and 5% of women, respectively.

Different types of media can act as a powerful tool to reach all people, even in remote rural areas. Most of the students knew about the transmission routes [11-12]. Similar observations were made in a study in Chennai where 86.7% of dental students were aware of the correct modes of transmission of the hepatitis B16 virus. % of students correctly identified the transmission modes, viz. blood transfusion, sexual intercourse, mother to child. Preventive measures were better known to our students compared to Study in Jammu, where they reported that the use of condoms and sterile needles was recommended by 20%, avoidance of addiction by 50%, and vaccination with hepatitis vaccine in 60% of women preventive measures against infection HBV [13-15]. Although

most students agree on the hepatitis B vaccine for disease prevention, nearly 40% of students have not taken the vaccine, mainly because of a neutral attitude towards HBV infection.

CONCLUSION:

Among medical students, almost 69% of students were unvaccinated, mainly due to a lack of motivation and a perceived need to vaccinate. These results show that awareness and motivation are essential to increase vaccination coverage.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the students had a good understanding of disease, transmission and prevention. Surprisingly, half of them were unaware of the high risk of passing on to them because of their medical profession. Almost 40% of students are unvaccinated and are at risk of contracting the disease in the future. Therefore, vaccination against hepatitis B is recommended for all unvaccinated students entering the medical profession. An orientation and sensitization program should be carried out to increase awareness of HBV infection.

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